

RESPONSE PAPER**LAST NAME: TOLLES****FIRST NAME: BENJAMIN****PROGRAM CODE: DCCTh****COURSE CODE : ACA-401D****PERIOD NUMBER: 6****INSTRUCTOR: DR. GULMA**

The author applied US conventions of grammar, usage, and mechanics :

The author did use Zotero to insert references

The author did use Grammarly Premium (provided by EUCLID)

My plagiarism rate (per Grammarly Premium) is: 0%

The author used the following software: Office 365 on Windows 10

QUIZ FOR COURSE ACA-401D

1. Course ACA-401D, like all EUCLID courses, is subdivided into how many periods?

7 Periods¹

8 Periods

6 Periods

5 Periods

2. Which citation style should be used in EUCLID Response Papers?

Chicago author-date style²

¹ Laurent Cleenewerck, *Student Orientation PDF* (Bangui: Euclid University, 2021), 2.

² Laurent Cleenewerck and Kabiru Gulma, *ACA-401/ACA401D Coursepack: Period 1*. Fourth Edition (Bangui: Euclid University, 2019), 41.

- Chicago notes-bibliography style
 - MLA parenthetical style
 - MLA narrative style
3. Kate L. Turabian's *A Manual for Writers* is the authoritative source for:
- Chicago Style³**
 - MLA Style
 - APA Style
 - ASA Style
4. EUCLID Papers require a plagiarism rate percentage as calculated by:
- Grammarly Premium⁴**
 - Zotero
 - Proofed
 - Upwork
5. Which citation style should be used in EUCLID Major Papers?
- Chicago notes-bibliography style⁵**
 - Chicago author-date style
 - MLA parenthetical style

³ Kate L. Turabian, *A Manual for Writers of Research Papers, Theses, and Dissertations: Chicago Style for Students and Researchers* (Chicago: The University of Chicago Press, 2018), xi.

⁴ Cleenewerck, *Orientation*, 3.

⁵ Cleenewerck, *Orientation*, 7.

- MLA narrative style
6. The best source for guidance on how to format a dissertation Title Page, Abstract, and Table of Contents would be:
- Bloomberg's *Completing Your Qualitative Dissertation***⁶
- Turabian's *A Manual for Writers*
- Cleenewerck and Gulma's *ACA-401D Coursepack*
- EUCLID University's *Student Orientation PDF*
7. Which link is *NOT* available at the lower left of the ACA-401D Page
- Grammarly plug-in**⁷
- Access to templates
- Access to checklists
- Student Orientation PDF
8. Which source refers to itself as a 'complete road map from beginning to end'?
- Bloomberg's *Completing Your Qualitative Dissertation***⁸
- Turabian's *A Manual for Writers*
- Cleenewerck and Gulma's *ACA-401D Coursepack*
- EUCLID University's *Student Orientation PD*

⁶ Linda Dale Bloomberg, *Completing Your Qualitative Dissertation: A Road Map From Beginning to End* (Los Angeles: SAGE, 2019), 6-8.

⁷Euclid University, *ACA-401D Course Homepage* (Bangui: Euclid University, 2023).

⁸Bloomberg, *Qualitative Dissertation*, xxv.

9. Periods 1-5 are different from Periods 6-7 in that:

- Study material is assigned in Periods 1-5⁹**
- Study material is assigned in Periods 6-7
- Major papers are assigned in Periods 6-7
- Periods 1-5 have quizzes

10. Students of what major may use WHO rules of style?

- Global Health students¹⁰**
- Theology students
- LLM students
- All Master's degree students

⁹ Cleenewerck, *Orientation*, 2.

¹⁰ Cleenewerck, *Orientation*, 2.

BIBLIOGRAPHY

Bloomberg, Linda Dale, and Marie Volpe. *Completing Your Qualitative Dissertation: A Road Map from Beginning to End*. Fourth edition. Los Angeles: SAGE, 2019

Cleenewerck, Laurent. *Student Orientation PDF*. Bangui: Euclid University, 2021.

Cleenewerck, Laurent and Kabiru Gulma. *ACA-401/ACA-401D Coursepack: Period 1*. Fourth edition. Bangui: Euclid University, 2021.

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Turabian, Kate L., Wayne C. Booth, Gregory G. Colomb, Joseph M. Williams, Joseph Bizup, and William T. FitzGerald. *A Manual for Writers of Research Papers, Theses, and Dissertations: Chicago Style for Students and Researchers*. 9th edition. Chicago Guides to Writing, Editing, and Publishing. Chicago; London: The University of Chicago Press, 2018.

Cleenewerck, Laurent and Kabiru Abubakar Gulma. 2025. ACA-401/ACA 401D Course Pack: Period 1. 6th ed. Washington, D.C.: Euclid University Press.
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15245536>.